

Management effectiveness evaluation in protected areas of southern Ecuador

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HIGHLIGHTS:

- PANE areas and private reserves showed higher management effectiveness.
- ABVP areas showed lower management effectiveness.
- Resource availability is the key factor in management effectiveness.
- Extension, age and location (province) are irrelevant.

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1 **Abstract**

2 Protected areas are home to biodiversity, habitats and ecosystem as well as a critical
3 component of human well-being and a generator of leisure-related revenues. However,
4 management is sometimes unsatisfactory and requires new ways of evaluation.

5 Management effectiveness of 36 protected areas in southern Ecuador have been
6 assessed. The protected areas belong to three categories: Heritage of Natural Areas of
7 the Ecuadorian State (PANE), created and funded by the State, Areas of Forest and
8 Protective Vegetation (ABVP), created but no funded by the State, and private reserves,
9 declared and funded by private entities.

10 Management effectiveness was evaluated by answers of managers of the protected areas
11 to questionnaires adapted to the socio-economic and environmental characteristics of
12 the region. Questions were classified into six elements of evaluation: context, planning,
13 inputs, processes, outputs and outcomes as recommended by IUCN. Results were
14 classified into four levels: unsatisfactory, slightly satisfactory, satisfactory and very
15 satisfactory.

16 The PANE areas and private reserves showed higher management effectiveness levels
17 (satisfactory and very satisfactory) than ABVP areas, where slightly satisfactory and
18 unsatisfactory levels prevailed. Resources availability was found as the main reason
19 behind this difference. The extension, age and province of location were found
20 irrelevant. Outputs, inputs and processes require main efforts to improve management
21 effectiveness. Improving planning and input in the PANE areas and inputs and
22 outcomes on ABVP areas is necessary to obtain a similar result in all areas.

23 **Keywords**

24 Management effectiveness; protected areas; National park; Tourism; Sustainable
25 development; Economic growth; Southern Ecuador

1 Introduction

Protected areas are the cornerstone of biodiversity, habitats (Craigie et al., 2010; Pandit et al., 2015; Venter et al., 2014) and ecosystem services conservation (Coad et al., 2008; Geldmann et al., 2015; Klein et al., 2007; Naidoo et al., 2006; Rodrigues, 2006; Scharlemann et al., 2010). In 2012, a total of 130,709 protected areas of various types were established globally, covering 24,236,479 km² of terrestrial (67%) and marine (33%) habitats (IUCN and UNEP-WCMC, 2012).

Protected areas are impacted by unprecedented global losses of biodiversity, habitats and ecosystem services mainly due to pressure from human activities (Craigie et al., 2010; Geldmann et al., 2014, 2013; Laurance et al., 2012; Zhang et al., 2016). Thus, management and effectiveness evaluation of protected areas are key factors for long-term sustainability (Joppa et al., 2013). Management effectiveness evaluation in protected areas is carried out in over 100 countries using over 50 different tools (e.g. approximately 5% of the world's protected areas have been evaluated so far) (Leverington et al., 2010). Evaluations have often been carried out because protected area founders (typically governments and non-government organizations) want to find out whether their investments in management have had the expected outcome.

The International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) has developed a framework for assessing management effectiveness. This allows to develop specific evaluation methodologies for a particular location with a global and consistent approach (Hockings, 2003; Hockings et al., 2006). In this framework, management effectiveness is evaluated by questionnaires answered by managers of protected areas. The questionnaires measure management inputs and outputs of protected areas to assess the strengths, weaknesses and management needs (Mascia et al., 2014).

The concept of protected area has evolved during the last decades. They are now considered not only important from an ecology point of view (Calado et al., 2016; Chape et al., 2005), but also as a critical component of human well-being (Bonet-García et al., 2015; Romagosa et al., 2015) and a generator of leisure-related revenues to sustain local economies (Ervin et al., 2010; Nyaupane and Poudel, 2011). Protected areas are the focus of increasing recreational and tourism interest and they are prime destinations for nature-based tourism due to their unique biological, natural and cultural features (Whitelaw et al., 2014). Protected areas constitute an important component of

1 the global tourism industry (Nyaupane and Poudel, 2011). They were a key attraction
2 for over 20% of the 990 million world tourists in 2011 (Buckley, 2009).

3 Developing countries in Southeast Asia, Africa and South America, have among their
4 priorities the reduction of poverty and the supply of food and commodities to their
5 citizens. Thus, in many cases, the conservation of protected areas is not a top priority
6 for some governments (Satumanatpan et al., 2014). However, developing a tourism
7 industry based on protected areas presents a golden opportunity for developing
8 countries to grow their economy. For instance, Ecuador has excellent conditions to
9 become an important tourist destination while protecting its ecosystems. It is one of the
10 most biodiverse countries in the world and much of its territory makes up some of the
11 34 global hotspots (Myers et al., 2000).

12 This paper proposes a methodology to assess the management effectiveness of 36
13 protected areas in southern Ecuador. Also, it aims to identify protected area
14 management strengths and weaknesses and test whether management effectiveness is
15 impacted by the type of area, extension, age and location of the protected area. Thereby,
16 this paper is intended to improve the management effectiveness of protected areas in
17 southern Ecuador.

18 **2 Materials and methods**

19 **2.1 Study area**

20 In this paper, 36 protected areas in southern Ecuador (Figure 1) were studied. Six areas
21 belong to the Heritage of Natural Areas of the Ecuadorian State (Patrimonio de Areas
22 Naturales del Estado, PANE, in Spanish). 23 areas belong to Areas of Forest and
23 Protective Vegetation (Áreas de Bosque y Vegetación Protectora, ABVP, in Spanish)
24 and seven are private reserves. The PANE areas were declared so and owned by the
25 State and are managed by a public entity that funds them. PANE areas belong to one of
26 the four subsystems of the National System of Protected Areas, run by the Ecuadorian
27 State. The ABVP areas are created by the State but may have different owners: public,
28 private or public-private entities and communities. Most belong to private owners and
29 do not have a public entity that manages and funds them. Private reserves are declared
30 and owned by private agencies that fund their management.

1 The southern region of Ecuador has an extension of 27,113 km² and 1,144,471
 2 inhabitants. From west to east, the provinces of El Oro (coast), Loja (Andes) and
 3 Zamora Chinchipe (Amazon) are located within this region. Loja is the largest with an
 4 area of 11,100 km² (400-3000 masl), followed by Zamora Chinchipe (10,454 km²,
 5 1000-3000 masl), and El Oro (5,792 km², 0-3600 masl). The population density differs
 6 in each province. El Oro has the highest density (90.77 inhab./km²; 600,659
 7 inhabitants), followed by Loja (38.26 inhab./km²; 448,966 inhabitants) and Zamora
 8 Chinchipe (7.3 inhab./km²; 91,376 inhabitants).

9 The southern Ecuador holds diverse ecosystems: island and marine-coastal areas,
 10 mangroves, dry forests, rainforests (pacific, montane and amazonic), moors, sandstone
 11 plateaus and semi-natural ecosystems, such as traditional policrops. It also overlaps two
 12 world biodiversity hotspots: Tumbes-Chocó-Magdalena and Tropical Andes
 13 (Mittermeier et al., 2005; Myers et al., 2000) and is home to 22 Important Bird Areas
 14 (IBA) (Birdlife International, 2005).

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16 *Figure 1. Protected areas studied in southern Ecuador. (Heritage of Natural Areas of the*
 17 *Ecuadorian State (PANE), green; Areas of Forest and Protective Vegetation (ABVP), orange;*
 18 *Private reserves, red).*

19 2.2 Methodology

20 The methodology used to evaluate management effectiveness in the three types of
 21 protected areas (PANE, ABVP and private reserves) was based on those proposed by
 22 the IUCN (Hockings et al., 2000), Stolton et al. (2003) and Ervin (2003). A modified
 23 version of the questionnaire proposed by Stolton et al. (2003) was used. This

questionnaire was adapted to the socio-economic and environmental characteristics of the region. The questionnaire (Table 1) included 38 multiple choice questions classified into six elements of evaluation: context (14), planning (8), inputs (4), processes (5), outputs (5), and outcomes (2). Each question had four possible answers. The interviewee was only allowed to choose one answer and each answer was assigned a score from 0 to 3. A score of 0 represented the worst management effectiveness and 3, optimal effectiveness. Six management effectiveness evaluation indices were calculated as a percentage of the maximum possible score. The management effectiveness score was calculated as the average of the six evaluation management effectiveness indices, following Hockings et al. (2000), Stolton et al. (2003) and Ervin (2003). Senior staff, usually high level managers, of 36 protected areas were interviewed from January to March 2012. Usually, these senior staff had degrees in forestry.

Table 1. Elements of evaluation, themes and topics included in the questionnaire for management effectiveness evaluation.

Elements of evaluation	Themes	Topic of question	
Context	Threats	Agriculture	
		Cattle raising	
		Civil construction	
		Deforestation	
		Tourism	
		Mining	
		Forest fires	
		Flora and fauna	
		Invasive species	
		Socioeconomics	Economic development
			Socio-environmental conflicts
		Politics	Government support
			Support from other Entities
			Local communities
Planning	Protected area design	Shape	
		Connectivity	
		Zoning	
		Boundaries	
		Objectives	Objectives
		Legal	Protected area creation
			Management and exploitation of natural resources regulations
			Regulations enforcement
Inputs	Staff	Full-time employees	
		Additional staff	
		Funding	Budget
		Logistics	Equipment and infrastructure
Processes	Planning	Local development plan	
		Management plan	
		Annual operative plan	
		Research and monitoring	Research and monitoring
		Activities	Environmental education and communication
		Outputs	Planning results
Penalties to users and employees			
Training	Employees		
Facilities	Visitors infrastructure		
Control mechanisms	Access to Protected Area		

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2 The six management effectiveness evaluation indices and the management effectiveness
3 scores were interpreted according to the scale suggested by Ulloa and Tamayo (2012).
4 This interpretation classifies the results into four categories based on the percentage of
5 the maximum possible score: <25%, unsatisfactory; 25-50%, slightly satisfactory; 50-
6 75%, satisfactory; 75-100%, very satisfactory. Unsatisfactory indicates that the
7 protected area has no guaranty of long-term permanence. Slightly satisfactory means
8 that the protected area is highly vulnerable to the confluence of external factors and its
9 permanence is not guaranteed in the long-term. Satisfactory indicates that the protected
10 area has deficiencies which prevent an effective management, but the management
11 objectives are partially met. Very satisfactory indicates that the permanence of the
12 protected area is guaranteed and management objectives are fully meet.

13 **2.3 Statistical analysis**

14 SPSS version 20 software was used to calculate the coefficient of determination (R^2)
15 among extension, age, province of location and management effectiveness scores. SPSS
16 was also used to carry out ANOVA tests. The latter determines whether there are
17 significant differences between groups and allows drawing conclusions about
18 management effectiveness.

19 **3 Results and discussion**

20 **3.1 Management effectiveness scores by type of area**

21 Figure 2 shows the results in management effectiveness. The highest values (average \pm
22 standard deviation) in management effectiveness scores corresponds to private reserves
23 (72.6% \pm 6.9, satisfactory), followed by PANE (68.4% \pm 9.7, satisfactory) and ABVP
24 areas (40.7% \pm 15.1 slightly satisfactory). However, there are only significant differences
25 ($p < 0.05$) between the ABVP areas and the rest. Between private reserves and PANE
26 areas there is no significant difference ($p > 0.05$).

27 Among private reserves, the highest management effectiveness score corresponds to
28 San Francisco (78.8%, very satisfactory) and the lowest to El Madrigal (61.7%,
29 satisfactory). In PANE areas, values range from 83.5% (very satisfactory) for Yacuri, a

1 National Park, to 55.26% (satisfactory) for Arenillas. Among ABVP areas, the highest
 2 value is for Dr. Servio (65.0%, satisfactory), followed by Petrificado Puyango (62.8%,
 3 satisfactory) and El Bosque (62.2%, satisfactory). For this kind of protected area,
 4 Susuco (18.2%, unsatisfactory) shows the lowest value.

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 6 *Figure 2. Management effectiveness scores (%) and element of evaluation (%) by type of*
 7 *protected area: Heritage of Natural Areas of the Ecuadorian State (PANE), Areas of Forest and*
 8 *Protective Vegetation (ABVP) and private reserves.*

9 Table 2 lists the results of management effectiveness scores. Private reserves dominate
 10 the top positions for management effectiveness. However, the protected area with the
 11 highest management effectiveness score corresponds to a PANE area, Yacuri (83.5%,
 12 very satisfactory), followed by three private reserves: San Francisco (78.8%, very
 13 satisfactory), Jorupe (77.5%, very satisfactory) and Utuana (77.1%, very satisfactory).
 14 The ABVP areas occupy the last places. The lowest management effectiveness score
 15 corresponds to Susuco (18.2%, unsatisfactory), followed by Ingenio Santa Rosa (19.5%,
 16 unsatisfactory) and El Guabo (20.3%, unsatisfactory).

17 Regarding the categories of the protected areas, all private reserves achieve a very
 18 satisfactory (n=4) and satisfactory (n=3) management effectiveness. The same occurs in
 19 PANE areas, with 1 very satisfactory area and 5 satisfactory areas. Results differ in the
 20 ABVP areas, where management in 35% of the areas (n=8) is satisfactory, 43% is
 21 slightly satisfactory (n=10) and 22% is unsatisfactory (n=5).

22 These results can be explained by the difference in resources in each kind of protected
 23 area. While private reserves and PANE areas have private and/or public resources, they
 24 are scarce in most of the ABVP areas. Within private reserves, San Francisco receives

1 investments in equipment and personnel thanks to research carried out in the reserve at
2 the San Francisco Research Station. Jorupe and Utuana reserves are dedicated to bird
3 watching, which helps their funding. Within the ABVP areas, the three areas with the
4 highest management effectiveness score also have resources available. Dr. Servio and
5 El Bosque have private support, while Petrificado Puyango has public support from
6 several local governments. Our results suggest that management effectiveness score is
7 higher when resources are available, regardless of whether these funds come from
8 public or private sources.

9 These results agree with those found by other researchers in nearby protected areas.
10 Mayorquín et al. (2010) found that Riomanso and Cabaña-La Esperanza private reserves
11 in Colombia, had very satisfactory and satisfactory management effectiveness scores.
12 The Ecuadorian Ministry of the Environment evaluated the effectiveness of
13 management in PANE areas such as the Machalilla National Park (73.5%, satisfactory)
14 (Ecuadorian Ministry of the Environment, 2007a) and the Cotacachi Cayapas (76.9%,
15 very satisfactory) (Ecuadorian Ministry of the Environment, 2007b). The effectiveness
16 scores found in this study (13.3-65.6%) are similar to those found by Ganzenmüller et
17 al. (2010) in eight ABVP areas of the Choco-Manabi conservation corridor
18 (northwestern Ecuador).

Table 2. Basic characteristics, evaluation areas and management effectiveness scores for the protected areas studied. Heritage of Natural Areas of the Ecuadorian State (PANE), Areas of Forest and Protective Vegetation (ABVP) and private reserves.

Type of protected area	Area name	Basic characteristics			Management effectiveness evaluation areas (%)						Management effectiveness score (%)
		Extension (ha)	Creation year	Main province	Context	Planning	Inputs	Processes	Outputs	Outcomes	
Heritage of Natural Areas of the Ecuadorian State (PANE)	Podocarpus	146,280	1982	Zamora	69.1	50.0	50.0	66.7	33.3	50.0	55.3
	Santa Clara	5	1999	El Oro	76.2	58.3	58.3	53.3	40.0	66.7	61.6
	Arenillas	17,082	2001	El Oro	66.7	66.7	66.7	66.7	66.7	66.7	66.7
	El Zarza	3,643	2006	Zamora	78.6	66.7	66.7	66.7	66.7	83.3	71.4
	Yacuri	43,090	2009	Loja	81.0	66.7	66.7	53.3	53.3	100.0	72.2
	Cerro Plateado	26,114	2010	Zamora	85.7	83.3	83.3	73.3	66.7	100.0	83.5
Areas of Forest and Protective Vegetation (ABVP)	San Francisco, San Ramón	30,621	1970	Loja	33.3	0.0	0.0	33.3	13.3	0.0	18.2
	Petrificado Puyango	3,917	1987	Loja	42.9	16.7	16.7	13.3	6.7	0.0	19.5
	Ingenio Santa Rosa	12,326	1987	Loja	42.9	8.3	8.3	20.0	13.3	16.7	20.3
	El Guabo	2,319	1988	Loja	50.0	0.0	0.0	26.7	6.7	0.0	21.5
	Santa Rita	2,141	1988	Loja	47.6	8.3	8.3	33.3	13.3	16.7	24.1
	Moro-Moro	3,131	1992	El Oro	28.6	25.0	25.0	26.7	26.7	33.3	29.6
	Susuco	103	1992	Loja	42.9	25.0	25.0	20.0	26.7	33.3	30.2
	La Chorrera	2,051	1993	Loja	45.2	16.7	16.7	40.0	20.0	33.3	32.1
	El Bosque	2,233	1994	Loja	47.6	25.0	25.0	40.0	20.0	33.3	34.6
	Jatumpamba – Jorupe	8,027	1996	Loja	52.4	25.0	25.0	26.7	26.7	33.3	35.7
	Casacay	12,577	1997	El Oro	52.4	25.0	25.0	46.7	33.3	16.7	36.7
	Hoya de Loja	10,752	1998	Loja	52.4	41.7	41.7	66.7	26.7	0.0	39.6
	Rumi-Wilco	26	2000	Loja	59.5	25.0	25.0	46.7	6.7	50.0	41.0
	Corazón de Oro	54,143	2000	Loja	59.5	50.0	50.0	20.0	40.0	50.0	44.2
	Dr. Servio	73	2000	Loja	59.5	25.0	25.0	46.7	26.7	50.0	44.4
	El Sayo	124	2000	Loja	57.1	25.0	25.0	46.7	46.7	66.7	52.2
	Alto Nangaritza	128,867	2001	Zamora	71.4	33.3	33.3	20.0	33.3	100.0	54.8
Zhique-Salado	85	2001	Loja	71.4	33.3	33.3	20.0	33.3	100.0	54.8	
Colambo Yacuri	79,731	2002	Loja	73.8	33.3	33.3	26.7	33.3	100.0	56.3	
Tukupi-Nunke	6,378	2008	Zamora	69.1	33.3	33.3	46.7	33.3	100.0	56.8	
Tiwi-Nunka	6,976	2008	Zamora	73.8	50.0	50.0	53.3	33.3	83.3	62.2	
Micha-Nunka	1,613	2008	Zamora	52.4	83.3	83.3	66.7	53.3	66.7	62.8	
Private reserves	Arcoiris	10	1996	Zamora	69.1	50.0	50.0	53.3	60.0	66.7	65.1
	San Francisco	1,100	1997	Zamora	69.1	50.0	50.0	53.3	60.0	66.7	61.7
	Utuaña	350	1998	Loja	69.1	58.3	58.3	66.7	40.0	66.7	64.7
	Chamusquin	41	2002	Loja	71.4	75.0	75.0	80.0	40.0	83.3	71.5
	Tumbesina-La Ceiba-Zapotillo	17,350	2005	Loja	81.0	58.3	58.3	66.7	66.7	100.0	76.7
	Jorupe	3,000	2005	Loja	76.2	91.7	91.7	66.7	53.3	100.0	77.1
El Madrigal	305	2005	Loja	78.6	91.7	91.7	66.7	53.3	100.0	77.5	

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* Zamora: Zamora – Chinchipe province.

3.2 Management effectiveness evaluation indices

The averages of the management effectiveness evaluation indices for the six elements of evaluation, i.e., context, planning, inputs, processes, outputs, and outcomes (Figure 2) show significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between the ABVP areas and the other two areas (private and PANE). However, no significant differences ($p > 0.05$) are found in any of the indices between PANE and private reserves. These results agree with those obtained for the management effectiveness scores.

Management effectiveness evaluation indices can be divided into two groups according to its averages (Figure 3). Context ($62.2\% \pm 14.9$), planning ($60.9\% \pm 20.2$) and outcomes ($58.3\% \pm 33.9$) show the highest averages. Processes ($46.7\% \pm 18.9$), inputs ($43.8\% \pm 26.9$) and outputs ($37.2\% \pm 18.8$) show the lowest averages. The first group show no significant differences within its elements of evaluation ($p > 0.05$). The same applies to the element of evaluation with lower average. However, there are significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in most evaluation indices of the high average group compared to the low averages. Only between outcomes and processes (those with closer averages) the difference is not significant ($p = 0.272$). Thus, it can be concluded that action is needed primarily on outputs, inputs and processes to improve the management effectiveness scores.

Figure 3. Averages of the six management effectiveness evaluation indices in the protected areas studied.

The difference between the average of management effectiveness score in private reserves (highest) and PANE areas is 4.1%. In the case of ABVP areas, it is 31.9%. The PANE areas show better management effectiveness in context (0.7%) and outputs (0.2%) than private reserves. However, differences are above 5% in planning (7.4%) and inputs (9.7%).

1 In the case of ABVP areas, the difference compared to private reserves is lower in context
2 (20.9%) and higher in inputs (46.4%) and outcomes (37.6%). It is a priority to improve the
3 planning and input indices in the PANE areas and inputs and outcomes in ABVP areas to
4 achieve similar effectiveness of management in all types of protected areas.

5 The highest score reached in the questionnaire corresponds to mining (context). Only in
6 Santa Rita and Alto Nangaritza there is illegal mining in the area. In all other protected
7 areas the situation is optimal, there are no concessions within the protected area.

8 Regarding tourism as an outcome, it shows an average score in the questionnaires. The
9 Ecuadorian Ministry of the Environment reports that over 2,000,000 people visited PANE
10 areas in 2015 (Ecuadorian Ministry of the Environment, 2016a). Around 100,000 during
11 the Carnival holidays (Ecuadorian Ministry of the Environment, 2016b). However, PANE
12 areas in southern Ecuador are among those with fewer visitors. It is probably due to several
13 reasons: being located far from the biggest cities of Ecuador (Quito and Guayaquil) and the
14 best known protected areas in the country, such as those in the Galapagos Islands and in
15 the northern half of the Ecuadorian Andes (including Chimborazo and Cotopaxi). It is also
16 affected by a lower proportion of coastal protected areas, whose beaches attract many
17 visitors. Thus, it is recommended to promote tourism in protected areas of southern
18 Ecuador through advertising to tours organizers and visitors, and improving roads. It is
19 also interesting advertising in the city of Cuenca, Ecuadorian third biggest city and
20 relatively close. Furthermore, Cuenca has a high proportion of foreign tourists and
21 residents who, in many cases, are attracted by eco-tourism. In fact, Cajas National Park,
22 very close to the city, registers an intermediate number of visits compared to other PANE
23 areas. The question with the lowest average score is that referred to visitor infrastructure.
24 According to the responses, there is an obvious lack of infrastructure for visitors. Thus,
25 improving this infrastructure is also important to increase the number of visitors and
26 improve their experience.

27 Deforestation shows one of the lowest average scores in the questionnaires. Ecuador loses
28 annually between 60,000 to 200,000 hectares of native forests and their primary forests
29 decrease at 1.8% per year, the highest rate in Latin America (FAO, 2016). Among other
30 reasons, deforestation is the result of illegal logging, pressure from oil and mining
31 companies and expansion of crops (favored by the recent rise in corn prices).

32 Food security can be achieved through agricultural intensification and measures such as
33 social protection, rather than through the expansion of agricultural areas at the expense of

1 forests (FAO, 2016). Linking agricultural incentives to environmental criteria, adopting
2 silvopastoral practices, paying for environmental services and the recovering of degraded
3 pastures can prevent the expansion of the agricultural frontier at the expense of forests.
4 Ecuador implemented such measures with the Sociobosque program and the National
5 Forest Restoration Plan and reduced deforestation by 4% per year, while worldwide
6 reduction was 1%.

7 **3.3 Impact of extension, age and province on management effectiveness** 8 **score**

9 The coefficient of determination (R^2) was calculated to correlate management effectiveness
10 scores and extension of protected areas. Correlation calculations were carried out for the
11 dataset as a whole and for each type of protected area separately. Results show that
12 management effectiveness and the extension of protected areas are uncorrelated. R^2 values
13 are less than 0.1 in all cases. These results agree with those found by Kolahi et al. (2013) in
14 Khojir National Park, Iran. This protected area showed low management effectiveness
15 despite occupying 10,000 ha in the core of a broader protected area (Jajrud) with more than
16 72,000 ha.

17 Average extension in PANE areas (39,369 ha) is greater than in private reserves (3,165
18 ha). While PANE areas are all over 3,500 ha (except for Santa Clara) with most of them in
19 the range of 3,500 to 45,000, all private reserves are below 3,000 ha (except for
20 Tumbesina-La Ceiba-Zapotillo). The question whether private areas similar in extension to
21 PANE areas would be equally effective emerges. Especially considering the difficulty for
22 private entities to obtain funds compared to the State, allowing the latter to manage greater
23 areas. Further research is necessary to elucidate this question.

24 Situation is similar when management effectiveness scores are correlated to the age of
25 protected areas. Again, R^2 were calculated for the dataset as a whole and for each type of
26 protected areas separately. R^2 obtained were lower than 0.15 in all cases, indicating that
27 management effectiveness is independent of the age of protected areas. These results agree
28 with those found by Kolahi et al. (2013) in the oldest protected area of Iran, the Khojir
29 National Park, with a low management effectiveness (43%, slightly satisfactory).

30 The averages of management effectiveness scores depending on the provinces of southern
31 Ecuador (El Oro, Loja and Zamora-Chinchipe) are very similar and show no significant
32 differences ($p > 0.05$). The highest average corresponds to Zamora-Chinchipe ($54.0\% \pm 17.7$,

1 satisfactory), followed by El Oro (53.8%±12.8, satisfactory) and Loja (50.2±21.5%,
2 satisfactory). Thus, the variables associated with the province described in materials and
3 methods section, such as population density, can not be considered significant.

4 **3.4 Methodology discussion**

5 Hockings et al. (2000) and Stolton et al. (2003, 2007) discuss the difficulties and
6 possibilities for distortion of integrating the scores obtained in the questions. Each
7 evaluation index is composed of different number of questions. Thus, calculating the
8 management effectiveness score as the arithmetic mean of the six evaluation indices, some
9 questions are valued more than others. For example, questions being part of outcomes (2)
10 will have seven times more relevance to the management effectiveness scores than those
11 belonging to context (14). Thus, in this work weights have been assigned indirectly to each
12 of the questions based on the grouping for the calculation of the management effectiveness
13 evaluation indices.

14 Weights could have being also added directly to each of the questions for calculating the
15 management effectiveness evaluation indices or to the management effectiveness
16 evaluation indices for calculating the management effectiveness scores. In these cases,
17 weights can be added according to the number of questions, the expert criteria (for
18 example, with the Delphi method) or statistical methods, such as the principal component
19 analysis (PCA) (Böhringer and Jochem, 2007).

20 Figure 4 compares the management effectiveness scores by the type of area as it is
21 calculated in this work and as the arithmetic mean of all the questions, without the
22 intermediate step of the management effectiveness evaluation indices. I.e., giving equal
23 weight to all questions. Management effectiveness score increases in all three types of
24 areas when all questions are weighted equally. This indicates that the questions with
25 greater weight, such as those of inputs (4) and outcomes (2), decrease the arithmetic mean.
26 Despite this, order in management effectiveness score remains equal: private areas
27 maintain the highest management effectiveness score, followed very closely by the PANE
28 areas and, lastly, ABVP areas.

29 Standard deviations have decreased in all three types of protected areas, facilitating to find
30 significant differences in management effectiveness. However, there are no significant
31 differences between the management effectiveness score in the areas according to the
32 weighting method used ($p>0.05$).

Figure 4. Management effectiveness scores calculated by both arithmetic and geometric means and weighting (calculating management effectiveness evaluation indices as a previous step) and not weighting (calculating means over questions).

It is also necessary to discuss whether it is convenient to integrate the scores of questions using the arithmetic mean. This method allows total compensability between questions (OECD, 2008). However, protecting an area requires achieving relatively good scores in all questions. Low scores on some questions could make the protection of the area and its long-term survival unviable, although other questions achieve high scores.

Using the geometric mean instead of the arithmetic would reduce compensability. Lower results would reduce the management effectiveness score significantly (Ebert and Welsch, 2004). In addition, the generalized implementation of the geometric mean would encourage to balance all aspects of protection and prevent from excel only in some, ignoring others. Figure 4 shows the management effectiveness score by the type of area calculated using the geometric mean for both management effectiveness evaluation indices and management effectiveness score. Nonetheless, geometric mean implies a higher dispersion of data, increasing standard deviation and making it more difficult to find significant differences. In this paper, the questions answered with 0 have been replaced by 0.01. Otherwise, it would not be possible to obtain a geometric mean.

Low scores on some questions could mean a serious threat for long-term survival of the protected area. Focusing on reducing compensability, this answers to the questions could be considered red flags. This would be a way of implementing a harder compensatory system, such as the non-compensatory multi-criteria approach (MEC) (OECD, 2008). Red flags could be also used as threshold scores for each management effectiveness evaluation index. Thresholds would be set by experts according to their relevance.

1 These results prove that it is important to justify the methodology used to aggregate and to
2 weight the results. If a random approach is used, the conclusions of the indexes can lead to
3 error.

4 **4 Conclusions**

5 The Heritage of Natural Areas of the Ecuadorian State (PANE, in Spanish) and private
6 reserves have the same level of management effectiveness score, rated as satisfactory and
7 very satisfactory.

8 The Forest and Protective Vegetation (ABVP, in Spanish) have lower management
9 effectiveness score than PANE areas and private reserves, prevailing levels slightly
10 satisfactory and unsatisfactory.

11 Higher management effectiveness scores are associated with the availability of resources.
12 While all PANE areas and private reserves have resources available, they are only
13 available in a few of the ABVP areas (those with better management effectivenesses).

14 Improving management effectiveness evaluation indices on the outputs, inputs and
15 processes is necessary to enhance management effectiveness score. Improving planning
16 and input evaluation effectivenesses in the PANE areas and inputs and outcomes on ABVP
17 areas is required to achieve a similar management effectiveness in all types of protected
18 areas.

19 The extension, age and province of location are not determining factors in the management
20 effectiveness score of the protected areas.

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Table

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Evaluation item	Title	Topic of question	Answers and scores			
			0	1	2	3
Context	Threats	Agriculture	Intense within the protected area and its buffer zone	In the buffer zones of the protected area and moving inward	Only in the buffer zone and in a sustainable manner	Non-existent within the protected area or its buffer zone
		Cattle raising	Intense within the protected area and its buffer zone	In the buffer zones of the protected area and moving inward	Only in the buffer zone and in a sustainable manner	Non-existent within the protected area or its buffer zone
		Civil construction	Civil works within the protected area	Infrastructure already built within the protected area	Works planned in the protected area and / or in the buffer zone	No civil works or planned in the protected area and the buffer zone
		Deforestation	Intense within the protected area and its buffer zone	Minimum within the protected area but intense in the buffer zone	Inexistent in the protected area and not intensive in the buffer zone	Inexistent within the protected area and its buffer zone
		Tourism	Carried out without any planning	Carried out illegally	Planned by a central authority but unfulfilled	Planned by a central authority and coordinated with the environmental authority
		Mining	Illegal mining in the protected area	Exploration or exploitation concessions are in operation in the protected area	Prospecting concessions are in operation in the protected area	No prospecting, exploration or exploitation concessions in the protected area
		Forest fires	Frequent and large scale within the protected area	Present within the protected area but it has a contingency plan	Present in the buffer zone but are quickly controlled	Non-existent in the area or in the buffer zone
		Flora and fauna	Present in the entire protected area	With large number of endemic and threatened species	Species trade and poaching is fairly controlled	Species trade and poaching is fully controlled
		Invasive species	Affect most of the protected area	Affect only part of the protected area and are difficult to control	Its effects are not recognized as harmful and are focused and controlled	Not present in the area
		Socioeconomics	Economic development	The protected area reduced the options for local economic development	The protected area did not affect the local economy	The protected area brought economic benefits to the local economy
Socio-environmental conflicts	Affect the entire protected area		Affect most of the protected area	Present but can be controlled	Non-existent	
Politics	Government support	Non-existent	Not significant	Significant but sporadic	Significant, continuous and efficient	
	Support from other Entities	Non-existent	Not significant	Significant but sporadic	Significant, continuous and efficient	
	Local communities	Without access to decision-making on protected area management	With access to decision-making on the management of the protected area but its suggestion are not taken into account	Involved in making some decisions about protected area management	Involved in decision-making about protected area management	

Evaluation item	Title	Topic of question	Answers and scores			
			0	1	2	3
Planning	Protected area design	Shape	Separated into several fragments	Irregular, at least part of the protected area	Uniform and continuous	Continuous circular
		Connectivity	Totally isolated from other areas	Almost isolated, with only small areas of connectivity	Directly connected with other areas but under anthropogenic pressure	Physically connected to other areas
		Zoning	Non-existent	Poorly determined	Determined but unfulfilled	Determined and fulfilled
		Boundaries	Not established	In the process of legal establishment	Legally established but not respected	Legally established and respected
	Objectives	Objectives	Not defined	Defined but unfulfilled	Defined and partially fulfilled	Defined and completely fulfilled
	Legal	Protected area creation	Not created legally	Created under an inadequate legal instrument because of the lowest level in the legal scale	Created under an inadequate legal instrument regarding political and social aspects	Created under an adequate legal instrument
		Management and exploitation of natural resources regulations	Non-existent	With marked conflicts among them	Define a framework for action although it is insufficient	Define a framework for effective action to ensure sustainable use
	Regulations enforcement	Users break and ignore regulations. The regulations enforcement is poor	Users usually break regulations. Workers perform some controls and inform about regulations sporadically	Users sometimes break regulations. Workers control regulations enforcement and inform about regulations	Users satisfactorily comply with regulations. Workers control regulations enforcement and inform about regulations	
Inputs	Staff	Full-time employees	Non-existent	Insufficient for critical management activities	Sufficient for critical activities but is not permanent	Adequate for area management needs and permanent
		Additional staff	Not possible recruitment	Great difficulty to recruit additional staff	Hired usually with difficult and late	Hired in an appropriate manner
	Funding	Budget	Non-existent	Inadequate and a serious obstacle for the effective management of the area	Acceptable but it requires improvement for effective management	Sufficient for effective management
	Logistics	Equipment and infrastructure	Non-existent or very little	Present but inadequate or insufficient	Adequate for the area, but the employees lack the ability to handle them	Adequate for the area and properly handle
Processes	Planning	Local development plan	Non-existent	Present but not running	It includes protected areas and partially executed	It includes protected areas and executed with good results for the protected area
		Management plan	Non-existent	Elaborating and updating	Present but not executed	Updated and under execution
		Annual operative plan	Non-existent	Elaborating and updating	Present but not executed	Updated and under execution
	Research and monitoring	Research and monitoring	Non-existent	Some sporadic research	Several research and monitoring, but not focused on the needs of area management	Research and monitoring programs according to the needs of management implementation
	Activities	Environmental education and communication	Non-existent	Programs not related to the protected area	Programs related to the area, but regularly not fulfilled	Programs related to the area in execution permanently

Evaluation item	Title	Topic of question	Answers and scores			
			0	1	2	3
Outputs	Planning results	Achievement of objectives of management	Management problems substantially limit the achievement of the objectives	Management problems partially limit the achievement of the objectives	Management is adequate to achieve most of the objectives	Management is excellent and achieves the objectives
		Penalties to users and employees	Non-existent	Mild	Severe but not enforced in accordance with the law	Severe and enforced in accordance with the law
	Training	Employees	Non-existent	Training programs designed but not implemented	Training programs implemented only partially	Training programs planned and implemented successfully
	Facilities	Visitors infrastructure	Non-existent	Services are not appropriate for the number of visitors or are being built	Services are appropriate for the number of visitors but clearly improvable	Services are excellent for the number of visitors
	Control mechanisms	Access to Protected Area	Non-existent	Insufficient	Sufficient	Abundant
Outcomes	Tourism		Present and affects the area	Moderately practiced without proper rules	Tourism activities with not trained staff	Tourism activities carried out sustainably
	Surrounding communities		Its impacts are evident in all areas of the protected area	Its impacts are evident in the protected area but are controlled by staff and community area	Its impacts are not evident	There are no significant impacts within the area